

Aflatoxin B₁ production: A time–water activity–temperature model

Sonia Marín^{*}, Laila Aldars-García, Francisco Molino, Antonio J. Ramos, Vicente Sanchis

Applied Mycology Unit, Department of Food Technology, Engineering and Science, University of Lleida, AGROTECNIO-CERCA Centre, Av. Rovira Roure 191, 25198, Lleida, Spain

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Aspergillus flavus
Aflatoxin
Predictive mycology
Probability
Temperature
Water activity

ABSTRACT

Aspergillus flavus occurs as a contaminant of various foods and animal feeds and can produce the mycotoxin aflatoxin B₁ that is a danger to human and animal health. Here, we develop models to predict the behaviour of *A. flavus* in maize extract agar and maize grains. Growth and aflatoxin B₁ production were recorded on maize extract agar at 20–35 °C and water activities from 0.84 to 0.90. We then obtained probability models—using temperature, water activity, and time as explanatory variables—based on data of growth and aflatoxin B₁ production. Additional data were generated under two dynamically changing temperature regimes. Initial water activity, and relative humidity during incubation, were recorded. Predicted probability of growth under dynamic conditions based on models built under static conditions depended on the temperature regime and substrate, concordance ranging from 66 to 100%, with lower concordances obtained for aflatoxin B₁ production prediction. Interestingly, aflatoxin B₁ production was higher on maize grains than on maize extract agar. Moreover, this work suggests that the safe water activity for a cereal may depend on the previous water activity and temperatures which may have allowed fungal growth and so trigger later toxin production under water stress.

1. Introduction

The structure and functionality of fungi, like for all microorganisms, are subject to the prevailing thermodynamic conditions. The key factors that act as determinants of fungal survival, growth and ecophysiology are temperature, water activity, and time albeit that fungi have evolved to be able to survive biophysical extremes (Magan et al., 2003; Bosch et al., 2021; Lloyd, 2021; Hallsworth, 2022). *Aspergilli* and closely related fungi (those in the genera *Aspergillus* and *Eurotium*) are among the most resilient in relation to their ability to retain metabolic activity at low temperatures (Chin et al., 2010; Hassan et al., 2016), at low water activities (Stevenson et al., 2017a, 2017b; Hegarty et al., 2018), and in other stressful conditions where a robust stress biology and high levels of energy generation are required (Cray et al., 2013; Paulussen et al., 2017).

Aspergillus flavus is an ubiquitous fungus in the soil where its growth is promoted by heat and humid environmental conditions. *A. flavus* produces aflatoxins, known to be carcinogenic. Maize is an agricultural product considered to be highly susceptible to fungal colonization and mycotoxins contamination worldwide (Schrenk et al., 2020), including *A. flavus* growth and aflatoxins production. Improper harvesting, storage or processing practices can lead to the occurrence of high levels of

aflatoxins in maize used as human food or animal feed.

Climate change is expected to have an increasing impact on the presence of aflatoxin B₁ in maize in Europe (Schrenk et al., 2020), as pointed out in 2016 by Battilani et al. (2016), and confirmed by several works reporting high incidence of aflatoxin B₁ in maize in Italy and Serbia, in 2003 and 2012, respectively as a result of hot and dry summer season (Piva et al., 2006; Levic et al., 2013; Bailly et al., 2018). According to estimates, in Australia and Asia the environmental temperature may rise to an extreme level capable of leading to the extinction of some mould species and making cultivation of a number of crops virtually impossible. The Latin-American scenario foresees significant temperature rises and a reduction in soil water content and crop productivity will drop. In North America, floods and high temperatures will lead to storage-related problems in favour of mould growth and mycotoxin production. In the southern United States, the production of tropical cultures, such as maize, may reach an optimum (Kos et al., 2023).

Although aflatoxin production occurs in the field, the increasing presence of *A. flavus* at harvest may compromise the safety of the grain during postharvest, mainly during the delay time before drying and also during storage, if not correctly done (Stutt et al., 2023). In order to improve the control in these steps, predictive models may provide

^{*} Corresponding author.

E-mail address: sonia.marin@udl.cat (S. Marín).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.funbio.2024.03.003>

Received 14 September 2023; Received in revised form 5 March 2024; Accepted 6 March 2024

Available online 13 March 2024

1878-6146/© 2024 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier Ltd on behalf of British Mycological Society. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

important knowledge about fungal behaviour, and enable manufacturers to reduce the number of tests required to ensure the quality and safety of products, and to establish an adequate safe shelf life of foods.

For microbiology in general, as well as mycology in particular, modeling cellular processes can be used as a powerful research tool (Dantigny et al., 2005; Hallsworth et al., 2023). Most of the studies in predictive mycology have focussed on the effect of environmental factors on fungal growth and mycotoxins production under static conditions. However, dynamic environmental conditions usually occur along the food chain. Unfortunately, less attention has been paid on such fluctuations. Only few mycological studies were developed under dynamic conditions (Gougouli and Koutsoumanis, 2010; Garcia et al., 2012; Kalai et al., 2014), and they usually modelled fungal growth and not mycotoxin production. Palacios-Cabrera et al. (2004) pointed out that changing the temperature conditions may stimulate fungal growth/mycotoxin production under certain circumstances. Then it is important to consider these fluctuations during the developing and validation of models, otherwise their applicability would be compromised. Prediction of mycotoxin production, and specifically of aflatoxins production, has been shown to be complex under static temperature levels due to the increasing and afterwards decreasing levels sometimes observed along time in *in vitro* experiments (Garcia et al., 2011a, 2013; Aldars-García et al., 2018; Norlia et al., 2020; Akinola et al., 2021; Pei et al., 2022), consequently in most of the studies the models have been developed at a given time point, and they describe the impact of environmental variables at that time, except in the interesting work of Lee et al. (2014) who developed primary and secondary kinetic models for aflatoxin B₁. To overcome this issue, a few studies modelled aflatoxin production under static temperature levels using probability models (Aldars-García et al., 2015; Pei et al., 2021), thus building prediction models under changing temperature is challenging.

The ability to grow and the amount of mycotoxin which a mould produces in a food depends completely on the ecological and processing parameters of the particular foodstuff, as well as on its genetic ability to synthesise the toxin. Besides, fungal growth does not imply necessarily the presence of mycotoxins. This is explained by the fact that not all the strains in a mycotoxigenic species are able to produce mycotoxins and, in addition, the conditions favourable to growth may not be conducive to mycotoxins production. Moreover, growth is an event which presents less intraspecific variability, and its kinetics is more known, than mycotoxins production. However, the prevention of fungal growth in all the steps of the food chain, would lead to the prevention of the mycotoxins presence in the final food product (Marín et al., 2008; Bukhari et al., 2023).

Considering all this information, we focussed in this work on probabilistic models, which predict the probability of a given event, such as fungal growth or mycotoxin production. The objective of this study was to develop predictive probability models to assess for the first time the effect of changing temperature and water activity on the growth and aflatoxin production of *A. flavus* at dynamic temperature conditions to establish suitable preventive strategies. Few studies of mycotoxins exist which include temporal series of data.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Fungal isolate

A. flavus UdL-TA 3.327, originally been isolated from maize grains, was used in the current study. Maize had been purchased from a wholesaler in Lleida, Catalonia, Spain, and the strain is deposited in the culture collection of the Applied Mycology Unit of the University of Lleida, Spain. Aflatoxigenic capacity had been proven on Potato Dextrose Agar at 25 °C, after 7 incubation days and determined by high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) (Aldars-García et al., 2015).

2.2. Media preparation

Maize Extract Agar 2% w/v (MEA): Maize extract was prepared by boiling 40 g of raw ground dry maize grains in 1 L distilled water for 30 min. The extract was then filtered and the amount of evaporated water was made up to adjust to 4% w/v of maize extract again. The water activity of the media was adjusted by the addition of certain amounts of glycerol-water based on a previously built calibration curve to obtain the desired water activity of each treatment and 2% w/v of maize extract in the medium (Marín et al., 1995). Next, 12 g of agar were added per litre of medium (for each water activity), autoclaved and poured into 90 mm sterile Petri dishes, which were prepared under aseptic conditions.

Maize grains: An HPLC initial analysis showed that aflatoxin B₁ concentration in the grain was under the limit of detection (LOD, 0.1 µg/kg). Dry maize grains (13% w/w moisture content) were autoclaved (15 min at 121 °C) in 1-L bottles filled with 300 g of maize grains. Once sterilised, the water activity was adjusted by aseptically adding the corresponding amount of distilled water to the maize grains to reach 0.87 a_w. Previously, a calibration curve had been built relating the amount of water to be added per g of maize and the water activity reached (García et al., 2011b). The bottles were cooled down to approximately 4 °C for 48 h with periodic hand-shaking during this period. After that, maize grains (25 g) were placed in 90 mm Petri dishes under aseptic conditions.

The water activity in all cases was determined on an AquaLab Series 3 (Decagon Devices, Inc., WA, USA), with an accuracy of ±0.003.

2.3. Experimental design

In order to build a model on MEA under static conditions, the growth and aflatoxin B₁ production of *A. flavus* was studied using a full factorial design, where factors involved where temperature and water activity. Four temperature (20, 25, 30 and 35 °C) and water activity (0.84, 0.86, 0.88, and 0.90) levels were included for the static experiments. Four dishes were prepared per each temperature/water activity combination (4 × 4 × 4, a total of 64 Petri dishes) and two dishes per each temperature/water activity combination were prepared (2 × 4 × 4, a total of 32 dishes) for controlling the water activity throughout the study.

On the other hand, experiments were carried out by exposing *Aspergillus* (both on MEA and maize grains) to a series of temperature ramps, by increasing and decreasing temperature over time. For both the MEA and maize grains, two temperature regimes were programmed into the incubators (Fig. 1) for this purpose.

- for the first regime, increasing at a rate of 0.43 °C per day from 22 °C (start of day 1) to 25 °C (end of day 7); increasing at a rate of 1.25 °C per day from 20 °C (start of day 8) to 30 °C (end of day 15); maintained at 30 °C to end of day 17; decreasing at a rate of -2 °C per day from 30 °C (start of day 18) to 20 °C (end of day 22); and finally maintained at 28 °C during days 23–25; and
- for the second regime, increasing at a rate of 1.25 °C per day from 25 °C (start of day 1) to 30 °C (end of day 4); maintained at 30 °C to end of day 7; increasing at a rate of 3.3 °C per day from 20 (start of day 8) to 30 °C (end of day 10); decreasing at a rate of -1.1 °C per day from 30 °C (start of day 11) to 20 °C (end of day 19); maintained at 20 °C to the end of day 22; and finally increasing at a rate of 2 °C per day from 20 °C (start of day 23) to 26 °C (end of day 25).

Regarding water activity, a low level (0.87–0.89), but still conducive for fungal growth was selected, thus, 0.89 a_w was set for the MEA experiments, while water activity in the maize grain experiments was 0.87. In this case, 10 MEA dishes at 0.89 a_w and 10 maize dishes at 0.87 a_w were inoculated. Additionally, four MEA dishes per condition and ten maize dishes were prepared for water activity determination throughout the study.

Fig. 1. Temperature regimes programmed for the dynamic temperature experiments. a) Regime 1, b) Regime 2.

2.4. Inoculum preparation and inoculation

A. flavus UdL-TA 3.327 was grown on potato dextrose agar (PDA) medium at 25 °C for 7 days. Spores were collected by scraping the surface of the dishes and diluting them in sterile water adjusted to the correspondent water activity value with glycerol, containing Tween 80 (0.05% v/v) and filtered through sterile glass wool into a tube. After counting the spores on a Thoma chamber, the spore suspensions were serially diluted to a concentration of 10^5 spores/mL.

Petri dishes (both MEA and maize grains) were inoculated with 5 μ L of the spore suspension (10^5 spores/mL), onto four equidistant points (four points per dish, ca. 500 spores per point). This made 16 replicate

observations (four dishes x four points) for model calibration, and 40 replicated observations (10 dishes x four points) for validation in changing temperature scenarios.

For the experiments at static temperature conditions, inoculated dishes of the same water activity were sealed with Parafilm M®, in order to keep water activity as constant as possible, placed in plastic containers and incubated at the corresponding temperature condition for 24 days. For the experiments at dynamic temperature conditions (both in MEA and maize grain), after inoculation, dishes were not sealed with Parafilm M®, and were placed in sealed containers for incubation at the different temperature regimes for 24 days. In this case, as Parafilm M® was not used, a variation in water activity was expected. Air relative

Fig. 2. Air relative humidity values monitored throughout the experimental time (relative humidity in Regime 1 (—), relative humidity in Regime 2 (---)), water activity predicted from relative humidity (water activity Regime 1 (----), and water activity Regime 2 (.....)) of maize experiments. Four water activity data points measured along experimental time in maize dishes: ■ Experimental water activity for maize under Regime 1 and ● experimental water activity for maize under Regime 2.

humidity sensors were placed inside the containers both under static and dynamic conditions in order to measure its variation with temperature. The relative humidity of the air inside the Petri dishes was not measured; instead, water activity measurements of the agar media and grain were taken along time (see Fig. 2, four measurements along time).

2.5. Growth assessment

For both MEA and maize grains, the initiation of growth in each inoculation point was followed till the end of the study (24 days), with the aid of a binocular magnifier.

2.6. Aflatoxin B₁ analysis

Maize extract agar (MEA): Aflatoxin B₁ production was determined from the first sign of growth up until the end of the incubation time (24 days) in different size colonies (from 3 to 18 mm of radius). A 5-mm diameter agar plug from the centre of each colony was weighed and introduced into 3-mL vials. After sampling, the dishes were taken back to incubation, for the assessment of the other colonies present in the Petri dishes which were not sampled. Methanol (1 mL) was added to vials and vortexed for 5 s. After being left stationary for 60 min, the extracts were shaken again, filtered (MillexR SLHV 013NK, Millipore, Bedford, MA, USA), dried in a nitrogen stream and stored at 4 °C until HPLC analysis. All extracts were resuspended in 0.5 mL of methanol + water (50 + 50 v/v) and a volume of 100 µL was injected into the HPLC system (Waters, Milford, MA, USA), using a C18 column (5 mm Waters Spherisorb, 4.6 × 250 mm ODS2). A post column photochemical derivatization system (LCTech detector, UVC 254 nm, Germany) was used and aflatoxin B₁ was detected by fluorescence ($\lambda_{exc} = 365$ nm; $\lambda_{em} = 455$ nm). The mobile phase (isocratic) was water + methanol + acetonitrile (70 + 15+15, v/v/v) and the detection limit of the analysis was 0.1 µg/kg of aflatoxin B₁, based on a signal-to-noise ratio of 3:1.

Maize grains: 5 g of milled sample were extracted with 15 mL of acetonitrile + water (60 + 40, v/v) solution shaken for 10 min. The extract was filtered through number 1 filter paper and 2 mL of filtrate were mixed with 14 mL of PBS. Then the diluted extract was cleaned up by passage through an immunoaffinity column (Easy-extract Aflatoxin, R-Biopharm Rhone Ltd., Glasgow, Scotland) at a flow rate of 2–3 mL/min. The column was then washed with 20 mL of PBS and left to dry. Aflatoxin B₁ was eluted from the column with 3 mL methanol + water (50 + 50, v/v), and 100 µL was injected into the HPLC system as before. The mean recovery rate was 79% when samples were spiked in the range 0.83–3.33 µg/kg.

2.7. Model fitting: probability of growth and aflatoxin B₁ production

All statistical analysis were carried out using RStudio (RStudio, Posit Software, PBC formerly RStudio, PBC), R version 4.3.1. Logistic regression was used to model the probability of growth (Eq. (1)) and aflatoxin B₁ production (Eq. (2)) as a function of water activity, temperature and time, using R statistical software with the *glm* (general linear model) function. Using the data generated under static temperature conditions, the binary values along time (0 = no visible growth/no aflatoxin B₁ detection; 1 = growth/aflatoxin B₁ detection) were adjusted by linear logistic regression. Thus, the models developed in the present study are not based on any biological and/or conceptual assumption.

$$\text{logit}(P_G) = \ln \frac{P_G}{1 - P_G} = b_0 + b_1 * T + b_2 * a_w + b_3 * t + b_4 * T^2 + b_5 * a_w^2 + b_6 * T * a_w + b_7 * t * a_w + b_8 * t * T \quad (1)$$

$$\text{logit}(P_{AF}) = \ln \frac{P_{AF}}{1 - P_{AF}} = b_0 + b_1 * T + b_2 * a_w + b_3 * t + b_4 * T^2 + b_5 * a_w^2 + b_6 * t^2 + b_7 * T * a_w + b_8 * t * a_w + b_9 * t * T \quad (2)$$

$\text{logit}(P)$ represents $\ln [P/(1-P)]$, \ln is the natural logarithm, P_G or P_{AF} are the probability of growth initiation or aflatoxin B₁ detection (in the range of 0–1), T is the temperature (°C), t is the time of incubation (days), a_w is the water activity and b_i are the coefficients to be estimated. The goodness of fit of the models was determined through the calculated percentage of concordance between observed and predicted values with a cut off of 0.5 probability.

Based on these previously generated models, predictions were performed for the non-isothermal scenarios. The approach of Koseki and Nonaka (2012) was used; in particular, they estimated the probability of the end of lag time for *Bacillus cereus*, but the same methodology could be applied here. Briefly, a R version 4.3.1 algorithm was built so that for each time point in the variable temperature regimes, it took the estimation from the previously built logistic model using the constant temperature regimes, taking as initial assumption that the previous temperature levels did not determine the predicted probability in a certain time point. However, as suggested by Aldars-García et al. (2015), the algorithm needs to include a memory correction. Thus, the mean temperature in the 10 preceding days was used as input temperature in the model. Water activity values were estimated at each time point under the variable temperature regimes as a function of initial water activity and relative humidity measured by the sensors (Eq. (3), (4), (5) and (6)). Moreover, the algorithm was made cumulative, as predictions lower than those of the preceding time point were not allowed.

The goodness of prediction under non-isothermal conditions was also determined through the calculated % concordance between observed and predicted values with a cut off of 0.5 probability.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Dynamics of water activity and relative humidity under non-isothermal regimes

In the experiment at constant temperature conditions, water activity measurements of MEA along time revealed no significant differences in water activity values, due to the use of Parafilm to seal the dishes. This allowed us to consider both temperature and water activity constant along time, consequently the probability models generated based on these data could subsequently be used for prediction of probabilities at variable regimes of both temperature and water activity.

Two different dynamic temperature regimes were tested in this work (dotted lines in Fig. 4 show the actual temperatures recorded by sensors located in the incubators, for this reason there are some unexpected deviations from the temperature regimes programmed, but these were momentary so unlikely to have impacted the biological data obtained). Through the incubation period, air relative humidity was recorded continuously, while four water activity measurements were taken along time both in agar and maize dishes. Relative humidity values monitored as affected by temperature are presented in Fig. 2. For the first regime, relative humidity varied between 60 and 75%, with a slight decrease along time, while for the second regime, relative humidity remained quite constant between 75 and 85%. Regarding water activity, it did not vary significantly along time in the agar dishes (thus it was not represented in Fig. 2), while it decreased significantly in maize dishes. For prediction purposes, the initial water activity was corrected using the relative humidity regimes. Whereas some aspergilli are biotically active in the low relative humidity range (at <70%), *A. flavus* strains have never been observed to be capable of growth in this range (Lee et al., 2018).

Although the variation of water activity in MEA was not significant under these particular temperature conditions, to obtain a general procedure, water activity was proposed also to be a function of initial water activity and the decrease in this case in air relative humidity (although in this case coefficients were mostly insignificant, and water activity was equivalent to initial water activity):

First regime:

$$a_w = \text{initial } a_w - 1.82e-04 * (\nabla RH) + 1.94e-06 * (\nabla RH)^2 \quad (3)$$

Second regime:

$$a_w = \text{initial } a_w - 7.23e-06 * (\nabla RH) + 7.45e-06 * (\nabla RH)^2 \quad (4)$$

Where a_w is water activity, RH is relative humidity and $\nabla RH = (\text{initial RH}) - \text{RH}$.

For predictions in maize grain, water activity was proposed to be a function of initial water activity, decrease in RH in this case and time (both functions and experimental points are shown in Fig. 2):

First regime:

$$a_w = \text{initial } a_w - 6.55e-04 * (\nabla RH) + 1.64e-04 * (\nabla RH)^2 - 5.04e-03 * \text{time} \quad (5)$$

Second regime:

$$a_w = \text{initial } a_w - 3.17e-02 * (\nabla RH) + 8.74e-04 * (\nabla RH)^2 - 5.04e-03 * \text{time} \quad (6)$$

Predicted water activity values, obtained after correction using ∇RH , correctly agreed with the experimental water activity measured experimentally (Fig. 2). Using this approach to determine water activity would allow to know water activity evolution in stored cereals in which the initial water activity is known and only relative humidity probes would be required, which are not expensive. The equations presented here are useful in this particular situation, however, for generalisation for longer time periods and increasing relative humidity values, time should be avoided in the equations and the relationship between water activity and relative humidity studied in depth. The knowledge and understanding of the evolution of water activity is highly important in the cereal chain to ensure quality and safety. An example of monitoring the influence of atmospheric temperature and extraneous moisture on the course of temperature and moisture of maize grain during the storage in both steel silos and floored warehouses can be found in Angelović et al. (2018).

3.2. Prediction of *A. flavus* behaviour under dynamic conditions

3.2.1. Growth prediction under dynamic conditions

Linear logistic regression on isothermal data led to the following model (all coefficients were significant, however overfitting probably occurred due to the high number of explanatory variables used):

$$\text{logit}(P) = 3834.88 - 18.38 * T - 8538.42 * a_w - 74.49 * t - 0.16 * T^2 + 4549.07 * a_w^2 + 31.33 * T * a_w + 80.99 * a_w * t + 0.37 * T * t \quad (7)$$

Fig. 3. Probability growth lines at 0.84 (dotted lines) and 0.88 a_w (continuous lines) at 20, 22, 25 and 30 °C based on modelling growth data in MEA with a linear logistic model.

The index of concordance of the developed model was 99%. Fig. 3 shows probability lines at 0.84 and 0.88 a_w , and at 20, 22, 25 and 30 °C. When temperature decreased from 30 to 22 °C, estimated growth was delayed about 3 days at 0.88 a_w , and about 10 days at 0.84 a_w . No growth was detected at 20 °C at 0.84 a_w after 24 days. When growth occurred, the increase from 0 to 1 probability was sharp. This narrow time range in the initiation of growth has been reported by several authors (Astoreca et al., 2012; Marín et al., 2012; Aldars-García et al., 2015), and usually occurs when multispore inoculum is used (Aldars-García et al., 2016).

When this model was used to predict growth probability under the dynamic temperature regimes, with water activity values coming from the above equations, there was a certain deviation, which differed when predictions were made in agar or in maize. Predictions in MEA are shown in Fig. 4. For the first regime, observed growth was delayed two days compared to the predicted one (93% concordance, suggesting some overfitting in the isothermal model calibration). Even though the predictions were carried out taking into account the mean temperature in the 10 preceding days (as suggested in Aldars-García et al., 2015), and initiation of growth occurred while temperature increased, growth was still predicted earlier than observed. A possible explanation of this small overestimation may be due to the corrected values for water activity and temperature (Fig. 5) (taking into account the conditions of the preceding days). Looking at the corrected values, 21–24 °C and 0.89 a_w were the conditions used for prediction in the first days, compatible with efficient growth and responsible of the slightly earlier growth prediction. For the second regime, there was a 100% concordance between observed and

Fig. 4. Observed growth probability (o) and predicted values (—) of *A. flavus* in MEA under dynamic conditions of a) Regime 1 and b) Regime 2. Dotted line represents the temperature along time.

Fig. 5. Corrected values for temperature and water activity (accounting for the 10 preceding days) used to predict growth under dynamic temperature along time.

predicted data in agar. In general good agreement was obtained for both dynamic regimes in MEA, and the few no concordant observed and predicted values corresponded to fail-safe scenarios in which growth is predicted but not experimentally observed.

The need to take into account the mean temperature of the 10 preceding days for the dynamic predictions suggests a memory effect on fungal behaviour due to the past conditions, as mentioned previously. Also, for bacterial growth, Juneja et al. (2009) included a memory parameter on the modelling of growth obtaining accurate estimations. These results suggest that the inclusion of a memory parameter will improve such predictions and then, it is required for the proper development of the non-isothermal models.

Validation was performed also on maize grains under both dynamic temperature regimes. For the first regime, there was a delay in 4 days in observed growth, compared to the predicted one, and in this case the index of concordance was 84% (Fig. 6). On the 6th day, observed probability was under 0.2 while predicted one had already reached almost 1. Looking at the corrected values for water activity and temperature (Fig. 5) (taking into account the conditions of the preceding days), 21–24 °C and 0.87 to 0.89 a_w were the conditions used for prediction in the first days, compatible with efficient growth in agar (Fig. 3), but not so much in maize according to results. For the second regime, a delay in 5 days occurred between observed and predicted data. On days 3–5 observed probability was 0 while predicted one was 1, and the index of concordance was 75%. Looking at the corrected values for water activity and temperature (Fig. 5), temperature was highly conducive to growth (25–29 °C) but water activity decreased from 0.85 to 0.75 before the 3rd day (Fig. 5). However, before water activity dropped, there was a chance for growth to initiate, and it was predicted as such, while in real maize growth only occurred later, when water activity newly increased to almost 0.80.

The overestimation of growth initiation in maize grains, apart from the slight deviance that may be attributed to the corrected water activity values used for predictions, must be due to the easier availability of nutrients in agar medium compared to maize grain. Although generation of growth data in agar media is easier and more reproducible than in maize grain, it has been reported several times that the availability of nutrients may affect the chances of growth, especially at marginal water activity values (Pardo et al., 2004; Mousa et al., 2013; Yogendrarajah et al., 2016; Norlia et al., 2020). Kapetanakou et al. (2011) reported that the substrate structure has an important effect on growth. Their results showed that *Aspergillus carbonarius* growth and ochratoxin A production decreased as medium viscosity increased. Thus, when we develop the predictive models on agar, and extrapolate them to a food matrix, the difference in substrate structure should be taken into account. The same conclusion was reached by Garcia et al. (2012) studying the effect of cycling temperatures on growth and mycotoxin production by *Fusarium graminearum* and *Fusarium verticillioides* on soybean agar extract and soybean seeds. The extrapolation of growth on agar to soybeans led to overestimated values. Also, Garcia et al. (2011b) modelled the growth of *Aspergillus parasiticus* and *Aspergillus ochraceus* under static marginal conditions, and validated the models in maize grains, peanuts and coffee beans. In general, their predictions gave an overestimation of times to growth when used for prediction in the food matrices. To overcome this deviation, either a correction factor from agar to real foods could be applied (to apply an additional percentage on the predicted times) or just assume that the predictions are in the fail-safe side, and use them directly.

3.2.2. Aflatoxin B₁ production prediction under dynamic conditions

Linear logistic regression led to the following model under isothermal conditions (all coefficients were significant):

Fig. 6. Observed growth probability (○) and predicted values (—) of *A. flavus* in maize grains under dynamic conditions of a) Regime 1 and b) Regime 2. Dotted line represents the temperature along time.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{logit}(P) = & -77.34 - 1.05 * T + 196.90 * a_w - 2.17 * t - 0.02 * T^2 \\
 & - 147.48 * a_w^2 + 5.72e-03 * t^2 + 2.37 * t * a_w + 2.42 * a_w * t + 1.6e-03 \\
 & * T * t
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{8}$$

The index of concordance of the aflatoxin B₁ production probability model developed was 82%. Fig. 7 shows aflatoxin B₁ production

Fig. 7. Aflatoxin B₁ production probability lines at 0.84 (dotted lines) and 0.88 a_w (continuous lines) at 20, 22, 25 and 30 °C.

probability lines at 0.84 and 0.88 a_w, and at 20, 22, 25 and 30 °C. In none of the cases the probability reached 1 during the 24 days. At 0.84 a_w the probability never reached the cut off value (0.5), while at 0.88 a_w this value was reached after 15, 19 and 23 days at 30, 25 and 22 °C, respectively. When aflatoxin B₁ production was detected, the increase from the 0 value was smooth. Models reporting mycotoxin production along time are scarce, mainly due to the high amount of work involved. Recently, Akinola et al. (2021) used a Centred Composite Design and Response Surface Methodology to describe aflatoxins production by *A. parasiticus* in wheat flour for 7–15 days under different conditions of temperature and moisture content. Marín et al. (2012) developed probabilistic models for growth and aflatoxin B₁ production by *A. flavus* on pistachio nuts as a function of time, temperature and moisture content. They reported a similar behaviour under static conditions, with decreased aflatoxin B₁ production probability with lower moisture content and temperature values, also reporting the smooth increase in the probability lines. However, under higher water activity levels (up to 0.95 a_w) the probability increase is steeper in paddy, and also steeper than in MEA at similar conditions, confirming a potential higher production in food matrices (Pei et al., 2021).

When our model was used to predict aflatoxin B₁ probability under the dynamic temperature regimes, with variable water activity coming from equations [5] and [6], there was a certain deviation, which differed when predictions were made in MEA or in maize (Table 1).

For the first regime in MEA, observed aflatoxin B₁ production was delayed nine days compared to the predicted one (only 66% concordance was observed in this case). Looking at the corrected values for water activity and temperature, predicted aflatoxin B₁ production took place at about 0.86 a_w and 25 °C, while experimentally occurred after this point, at water activity 0.83 to 0.84 and 27 °C, but with a longer adaptation period. For the second regime, aflatoxin B₁ was not detected experimentally in 24 days, and according to the model probability of 0.5 was only reached in the 22nd day (87% concordance). Obviously, the dynamic conditions impose some kind of stress in the fungus, which is not reflected in the predictive model.

Validation in maize grain, for both regimes, showed higher probability of aflatoxin B₁ production in maize than those predicted by the models in agar. Surprisingly, aflatoxin B₁ was detected experimentally at day 8 for both regimes, and observed probability reached 100% after 21 days in the first regime and after 10 days in the second one. Looking at the corrected values for water activity and temperature, experimental aflatoxin B₁ production occurred at the higher temperature in the first regime, although this coincided with the lower water activity levels. For the second regime, observed aflatoxin B₁ production occurred at about 28 °C even though water activity was about 0.77. Consequently, aflatoxin B₁ production took place at the optimal temperature level despite of the low water activity levels, under which the model would not predict any production. Thus, as models were based on data generated in agar, it seems clear that even if temperature fluctuations may limit the potential for aflatoxin B₁ biosynthesis, maize grain may trigger it, compared to agar.

These results, both in MEA and maize grain, highlight that mycotoxin production is a complex event, where many factors are involved. In maize grain, aflatoxin B₁ was detected under low water activity conditions, following periods of more suitable values, which may suggest that after these periods an imposed stress may trigger toxin biosynthesis. Schmidt-Heydt et al. (2009) studied the aflatoxin biosynthesis gene cluster under several environmental conditions. They reported that certain combinations of temperature and water activity which imposed stress on the fungus result in a reduction of the growth rate and an induction of the aforementioned cluster. Similarly, Ma et al. (2021) working with *A. flavus* and peanuts found that aflatoxin B₁ yield and conidia production were higher at lower water activity. Based on transcriptome data and RT-qPCR analyses, they noticed that most of the aflatoxin biosynthesis genes were more up-regulated in water activity 0.90 than water activity 0.95 and 0.99. The initial-step aflatoxin genes

Table 1

Probabilities observed (P_{observed}) from empirical data versus predicted probabilities ($P_{\text{predicted}}$) (using models built in MEA under isothermal conditions) for aflatoxin B₁ production along time (24 d) in both MEA and maize grains for the two changing temperature regimes.

Time (days)	P_{observed} MEA	$P_{\text{predicted}}$ MEA	%overestimation	P_{observed} maize	$P_{\text{predicted}}$ maize	%underestimation
Regime 1						
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	0	0.09	0	0	0.08	0
10	0	0.22	0	0.5	0.26	48%
15	0	0.51	∞	0.5	0.26	48%
20	0	0.72	∞	0.75	0.26	65%
24	1	0.99	0	1	0.26	74%
Regime 2						
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	0	0.28	0	0	0.12	0
10	0	0.40	0	1	0.32	68%
15	0	0.40	0	0.75	0.32	57%
20	0	0.40	0	–	0.32	–
24	0	0.88	∞	–	0.32	–

Shaded cells indicate lack of concordance (cut off = 0.5).

were slightly or moderately changed, while the middle- or later-step genes showed drastic responses to different water activity conditions. Furthermore, substrate may play an important role in mycotoxin production, since sometimes aflatoxin B₁ was produced in maize grains but not in agar medium under the same conditions (Regime 2). The previously mentioned study conducted by Garcia et al. (2012), reported a similar trend: under certain environmental conditions, *F. graminearum* produced DON in soybeans but not in agar medium.

3.3. Relationship between observed growth and aflatoxin B₁ production

For the first regime, observed growth occurred after 6 days in MEA and 9 days in maize grain, while aflatoxin B₁ production was delayed till 23 days in MEA and 21 days in maize. Such later observation was different from what was expected, as production in MEA was expected to occur earlier than in maize. For the second regime, observed growth occurred after 2 days in MEA and 7 days in maize, while aflatoxin B₁ production was not detected in MEA and was delayed till the 10th day in maize. Again, aflatoxin B₁ production in MEA was poorer than in maize. Thus, it seems that the real impact of the decreasing water activity in maize is not so limiting for aflatoxin B₁ production; probably once growth had occurred in the kernels, the decrease in water activity instead of preventing from toxin production, triggered it. Mycotoxin production, as secondary metabolism, is expected to occur parallel to growth but delayed in time. Thus, in our experiments, once growth occurred, in spite of the dramatic decrease of water activity, aflatoxin B₁ was synthesised. Besides, under the same conditions, once growth occurred, it took less time to produce aflatoxin B₁ in maize grains than in agar medium. For the first regime, 17 and 12 days separated growth initiation and aflatoxin B₁ production, in MEA and maize grains, respectively. For Regime 2, no aflatoxin B₁ was detected in MEA and it was detected after 3 days of growth initiation in maize grains. As far as we know, no similar observation has been reported before in the literature, mainly due to the scarce number of studies that determine fungal growth and mycotoxin production on both agar medium and a food matrix along time. In 2019 Garcia-Cela et al., 2019 suggested modelling of CO₂ production data from stored maize as an early indicator of the initiation of fungal or indeed pest activity which can be linked to the potential for mycotoxin production. They suggested that at approx. 0.56 % dry matter loss in maize contaminated with *A. flavus* may represent an increased risk of aflatoxin B₁ contamination levels being above the legislative limits for food.

The conditions of water activity and temperature used in this study simulate those occurring in harvested moist maize in the time period before drying without temperature control. This often occurs due to shortage of capacity in the drying infrastructures. Our results indicate

that growth is likely to initiate in only 5 days. Moreover, it has been shown that such growth may lead to increased toxin accumulation once the grain is dried if the water activity is not kept low enough (in case of water condensation).

In conclusion, in the present work, growth and toxin production under non-isothermal conditions was tried to be predicted for the first time. This led to acceptable growth predictions in MEA, however, the experimental design of this work is limited and there is still a gap between growth and toxin production in MEA and those in real food substrates. Thus, future work in this area should be focussed on a wider choice of temperature shifts, and an improved modelling of water activity as a function of temperature, and prediction of toxin accumulation on foods from growth data or toxin data generated in such foods. Moreover, this work suggests that the safe water activity level for a cereal may depend on the previous water activity and temperature levels which may have allowed fungal growth which may trigger later toxin production under water stress.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the EU funded Project 101079173-FunShield4Med (HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-03) and the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation (Project PID 2020-114836RB-I00 funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033).

In loving memory of Dr. Naresh Magan (1953–2023), our cherished friend, a true mycology enthusiast. We are grateful for the remarkable opportunity we had to work together on the challenging world of fungi and their ecophysiology. Naresh's passion and his deep understanding of fungal ecosystems brought a unique dimension to our research. Naresh's knowledge and dedication were unparalleled, and his infectious enthusiasm inspired us all. Naresh's legacy will forever endure, leaving an indelible impact on our understanding of the many secrets of fungi.

References

- Akinola, S.A., Ateba, C.N., Mwanza, M., 2021. Behaviour of *Aspergillus parasiticus* in aflatoxin production as influenced by storage parameters using response surface methodology approach. *Int. J. Food Microbiol.* 357, 109369.
- Aldars-García, L., Ramos, A.J., Sanchis, V., Marín, S., 2015. An attempt to model the probability of growth and aflatoxin B₁ production of *Aspergillus flavus* under non-isothermal conditions in pistachio nuts. *Food Microbiol.* 51, 117–129.
- Aldars-García, L., Sanchis, V., Ramos, A.J., Marín, S., 2016. Single vs multiple-spore inoculum effect on growth kinetic parameters and modeled probabilities of growth and aflatoxin B₁ production of *Aspergillus flavus* on pistachio extract agar. *Int. J. Food Microbiol.* 243, 28–35.
- Aldars-García, L., Berman, M., Ortiz, J., Ramos, A.J., Marín, S., 2018. Probability models for growth and aflatoxin B₁ production as affected by intraspecies variability in *Aspergillus flavus*. *Food Microbiol.* 72, 166–175.

- Angelović, M., Kristof, K., Jobbágy, J., Findura, P., Krizan, M., 2018. The effect of conditions and storage time on course of moisture and temperature of maize grains. *BIO Web of Conf.* 10, 02001.
- Astoreca, A., Vaamonde, G., Dalcerio, A., Ramos, A.J., Marín, S., 2012. Modelling the effect of temperature and water activity of *Aspergillus flavus* isolates from corn. *Int. J. Food Microbiol.* 156, 60–67.
- Bailey, S., El Mahgubi, A., Carvajal-Campos, A., Lorber, S., Puel, O., Oswald, I.P., Bailey, J.D., Orlando, B., 2018. Occurrence and identification of *Aspergillus* Section Flavi in the context of the emergence of aflatoxins in French maize. *Toxins* 10, 525.
- Battilani, P., Toscano, P., Van der Fels-Klerx, H.J., Moretti, A., Camardo Leggieri, M., Brera, C., Rortais, A., Goumperis, T., Robinson, T., 2016. Aflatoxin B1 contamination in maize in Europe increases due to climate change. *Sci. Rep.* 6, 24328.
- Bosch, J., Varliero, G., Hallsworth, J.E., Dallas, T.D., Hopkins, D., Frey, B., Kong, W., Lebre, P., Makhallanyane, T.P., Cowan, D.A., 2021. Microbial anhydrobiosis. *Environ. Microbiol.* 23, 6377–6390.
- Bukhari, S.H., Asghar, M.A., Ahmed, F., Jabeen, S., 2023. The production of aflatoxin B1 by *Aspergillus parasiticus* in peanuts and walnuts under the influence of controlled temperature and water activity. *Int. J. Food Eng.* 19, 551–560.
- Chin, J.P., Megaw, J., Magill, C.L., Nowotarski, K., Williams, J.P., Bhagana, P., Linton, M., Patterson, M.F., Underwood, G.J.C., Mswaka, A.Y., Hallsworth, J.E., 2010. Solutes determine the temperature windows for microbial survival and growth. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.* 107, 7835–7840.
- Cray, J.A., Bell, A.N.W., Bhagana, P., Mswaka, A.Y., Timson, D.J., Hallsworth, J.E., 2013. The biology of habitat dominance; can microbes behave as weeds? *Microb. Biotechnol.* 6, 453–492.
- Dantigny, P., Guilmar, A., Bensoussan, M., 2005. Basis of predictive mycology. *Int. J. Food Microbiol.* 100, 187–196.
- García, D., Ramos, A.J., Sanchis, V., Marín, S., 2011a. Is intraspecific variability of growth and mycotoxin production dependent on environmental conditions? A study with *Aspergillus carbonarius* isolates. *Int. J. Food Microbiol.* 144, 432–439.
- García, D., Ramos, A.J., Sanchis, V., Marín, S., 2011b. Modelling the effect of temperature and water activity in the growth boundaries of *Aspergillus ochraceus* and *Aspergillus parasiticus*. *Food Microbiol.* 28, 406–417.
- García, D., Barros, G., Chulze, S., Ramos, A.J., Sanchis, V., Marín, S., 2012. Impact of cycling temperatures on *Fusarium verticillioides* and *Fusarium graminearum* growth and mycotoxins production in soybean. *J. Sci. Food Agric.* 92, 2952–2959.
- García, D., Ramos, A.J., Sanchis, V., Marín, S., 2013. Modeling kinetics of aflatoxin production by *Aspergillus flavus* in maize-based medium and maize grain. *Int. J. Food Microbiol.* 162, 182–189.
- García-Cela, E., Kiaitsia, E., Sulyok, M., Krška, R., Medina, A., Petit Damico, I., Magan, N., 2019. Influence of storage environment on maize grain: CO₂ production, dry matter losses and aflatoxins contamination. *Food Addit. Contam.* 36, 175–185 part A.
- Gougouli, M., Koutsoumanis, K.P., 2010. Modelling growth of *Penicillium expansum* and *Aspergillus niger* at constant and fluctuating temperature conditions. *Int. J. Food Microbiol.* 140, 254–262.
- Hallsworth, J.E., 2022. Water is a preservative of microbes. *Microb. Biotechnol.* 15, 191–214.
- Hallsworth, J.E., Udaondo, Z., Pedrós-Alió, C., Höfer, J., Benison, K.C., Lloyd, K.G., Cordero, R.J.B., de Campos, C.B.L., Yakimov, M.M., Amils, R., 2023. Scientific novelty beyond the experiment. *Microb. Biotechnol.* 16, 1131–1173.
- Hassan, N., Rafiq, M., Hayat, M., Shah, A.A., Hasan, F., 2016. Psychrophilic and psychrotrophic fungi: a comprehensive review. *Rev. Environ. Sci. Biotechnol.* 15, 147–172.
- Hegarty, B., Dannemiller, K.C., Peccia, J., 2018. Gene expression of indoor fungal communities under damp building conditions: implications for human health. *Indoor Air* 28, 548–558.
- Juneja, V.K., Marks, H., Thippareddi, H., 2009. Predictive model for growth of *Clostridium perfringens* during cooling of cooked ground chicken. *Innovative Food Sci. Emerging Technol.* 10, 260–266.
- Kalai, S., Bensoussan, M., Dantigny, P., 2014. Lag time for germination of *Penicillium chrysogenum* conidia is induced by temperature shifts. *Food Microbiol.* 42, 149–153.
- Kapetanakou, A.E., Ampavi, A., Yanniotis, S., Drosinos, E.H., Skandamis, P.N., 2011. Development of a model describing the effect of temperature, water activity and (gel) structure on growth and ochratoxin A production by *Aspergillus carbonarius* in vitro and evaluation in food matrices of different viscosity. *Food Microbiol.* 28, 727–735.
- Kos, J., Anić, M., Radić, B., Zadravec, M., Janić Hajnal, E., Pleadin, J., 2023. Climate change—a global threat resulting in increasing mycotoxin occurrence. *Foods* 12, 2704.
- Koseki, S., Nonaka, J., 2012. Alternative approach to modeling bacterial lag time, using logistic regression as a function of time, temperature, pH, and sodium chloride concentration. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* 78, 6103–6112.
- Lee, C.J.D., McMullan, P.E., O’Kane, C.J., Stevenson, A., Santos, I.C., Roy, C., Ghosh, W., Mancinelli, R.L., Mormile, M.R., McMullan, G., Banciu, H.L., Fares, M.A., Benison, K.C., Oren, A., Dyal-Smith, M.L., Hallsworth, J.E., 2018. NaCl-saturated brines are thermodynamically moderate, rather than extreme, microbial habitats. *FEMS (Fed. Eur. Microbiol. Soc.) Microbiol. Rev.* 42, 672–693.
- Lee, S., Yoon, Y., Kim, D.M., Kim, D.S., Park, K.H., Chun, H.S., 2014. Mathematical models to predict kinetic behavior and aflatoxin production of *Aspergillus flavus* under various temperature and water activity conditions. *Food Sci. Biotechnol.* 23 (3), 975–982.
- Levic, J., Gosic-Dondo, S., Ivanovic, G., Stankovic, S., Krnjaja, V., Bocarov-Stancic, A., Stepanic, A., 2013. An outbreak of *Aspergillus* species in response to environmental conditions in Serbia. *Pesticides and Phytomedicine* 28, 167–179.
- Lloyd, K.G., 2021. Time as a microbial resource. *Environ. Microbiol. Rep.* 13, 18–21.
- Ma, L., Li, X., Ma, X., Yu, Q., Yu, X., Liu, Y., Nie, C., Zhang, Y., Xing, F., 2021. The regulatory mechanism of water activities on aflatoxins biosynthesis and conidia development, and transcription factor AtfB is involved in this regulation. *Toxins* 13, 431.
- Magan, N., Hope, R., Cairns, V., Aldred, D., 2003. Post-harvest fungal ecology: impact of fungal growth and mycotoxin accumulation in stored grain. *Eur. J. Plant Pathol.* 109, 723–730.
- Marín, S., Sanchis, V., Magan, N., 1995. Water activity, temperature, and pH effects on growth of *Fusarium moniliforme* and *Fusarium proliferatum* isolates from maize. *Can. J. Microbiol.* 4, 1063–1070.
- Marín, S., Hodzic, I., Ramos, A.J., Sanchis, V., 2008. Predicting the growth/no-growth boundary and ochratoxin A production by *Aspergillus carbonarius* in pistachio nuts. *Food Microbiol.* 25, 683–689.
- Marín, S., Ramos, A.J., Sanchis, V., 2012. Modelling *Aspergillus flavus* growth and aflatoxins production in pistachio nuts. *Food Microbiol.* 32, 378–388.
- Mousa, W., Ghazali, F.M., Jinap, S., Ghazali, H.M., Radu, S., 2013. Modeling growth rate and assessing aflatoxins production by *Aspergillus flavus* as a function of water activity and temperature on polished and brown rice. *J. Food Sci.* 78, M56–M63.
- Norlia, M., Jinap, S., Nor-Khaizura, M.A.R., Radu, S., John, J.M., Rahman, M.A.H., Peter, M.L., Sharif, Z., 2020. Modelling the effect of temperature and water activity on the growth rate of *Aspergillus flavus* and aflatoxin production in peanut meal extract agar. *Int. J. Food Microbiol.* 335, 108836.
- Palacios-Cabrera, H., Taniwaki, M.H., Menezes, H.C., Iamanaka, B.T., 2004. The production of ochratoxin A by *Aspergillus ochraceus* in raw coffee at different equilibrium relative humidity and under alternating temperatures. *Food Control* 15, 531–535.
- Pardo, E., Marín, S., Sanchis, V., Ramos, A.J., 2004. Prediction of fungal growth and ochratoxin A production by *Aspergillus ochraceus* on irradiated barley grain as influenced by temperature and water activity. *Int. J. Food Microbiol.* 95, 79–88.
- Paulussen, C., Hallsworth, J.E., Álvarez-Pérez, S., Nierman, W.C., Hamill, P.G., Blain, D., Rediers, H., Lievens, B., 2017. Ecology of aspergillosis: insights into the pathogenic potency of *Aspergillus fumigatus* and some other *Aspergillus* species. *Microb. Biotechnol.* 10, 296–322.
- Pei, P., Xiong, K., Wang, X., Sun, B., Zhao, Z., Xu, J., Jin, X., Ye, H., Xiao, J., Kong, J., 2021. Modelling the effect of environmental factors on the growth of *Aspergillus parasiticus* and mycotoxin production in paddy during storage. *J. Stored Prod. Res.* 93, 101846.
- Pei, P., Xiong, K., Wang, X., Sun, B., Zhao, Z., Zhang, X., Yu, J., 2022. Predictive growth kinetic parameters and modelled probabilities of deoxynivalenol production by *Fusarium graminearum* on wheat during simulated storing conditions. *J. Appl. Microbiol.* 133, 349–361.
- Piva, G., Battilani, P., Pietri, A., 2006. Emerging issues in southern Europe: aflatoxins in Italy. In: Barug, D., Bhatnagar, D., van Egmond, H.P., van der Kamp, J.W., van Osenbruggen, W.A., Visconti, A. (Eds.), *The Mycotoxin Factbook. Food & Feed Topics*. Wageningen Academic Publishers, Wageningen, The Netherlands, pp. 139–153.
- Schmidt-Heydt, M., Abdel-Hadi, A., Magan, N., Geisen, R., 2009. Complex regulation of the aflatoxin biosynthesis gene cluster of *Aspergillus flavus* in relation to various combinations of water activity and temperature. *Int. J. Food Microbiol.* 135, 231–237.
- EFSA CONTAM Panel (EFSA Panel on Contaminants in the Food Chain), Schrenk, D., Bignami, M., Bodin, L., Chipman, J.K., del Mazo, J., Grasl-Kraupp, B., Hogstrand, C., Hoogenboom, L.R., Leblanc, J.-C., Nebbia, C.S., Nielsen, E., Ntzani, E., Petersen, A., Sand, S., Schwerdtle, T., Vlemincx, C., Marko, D., Oswald, I.P., Piersma, A., Routledge, M., Schlatter, J., Baert, K., Gergelova, P., Wallace, H., 2020. Scientific opinion—Risk assessment of aflatoxins in food, 2020 EFSA J. 18 (3), 6040, 112.
- Stevenson, A., Hamill, P.G., O’Kane, C.J., Kminek, G., Rummel, J.D., Voytek, M.A., Dijksterhuis, J., Hallsworth, J.E., 2017a. *Aspergillus penicillioides* differentiation and cell division at 0.585 water activity. *Environ. Microbiol.* 19, 687–697.
- Stevenson, A., Hamill, P.G., Dijksterhuis, J., Hallsworth, J.E., 2017b. Water-, pH- and temperature relations of germination for the extreme xerophiles *Xeromyces bisporus* (FRR 0025), *Aspergillus penicillioides* (JHO6THJ) and *Eurotium halophilicum* (FRR 2471). *J. Microb. Biotechnol.* 10, 330–340.
- Stutt, R.O.J.H., Castle, M.D., Markwell, P., Baker, R., Gilligan, C.A., 2023. An integrated model for pre- and post-harvest aflatoxin contamination in maize. *Sci. Food* 7, 60.
- Yogendraiah, P., Vermeulen, A., Jaccsens, L., Mavromichali, E., De Saeger, S., De Meulenaer, B., Devlieghere, F., 2016. Mycotoxin production and predictive modelling kinetics on the growth of *Aspergillus flavus* and *Aspergillus parasiticus* isolates in whole black peppercorns (*Piper nigrum* L.). *Int. J. Food Microbiol.* 228, 44–57.